

Attribute-Based Modeling Framework for Life Cycle Assessment: Conceptual Mapping, Cause–Effect Structures, and Attribute Specification

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Abstract

This research compendium supports the study *"Attribute-Based Modeling for Life Cycle Assessment: from Linking Components to Improvement Implications"* by providing the foundational conceptual and structural materials underlying the proposed attribute-based modeling framework for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).

The material formalizes a systematic approach for extracting, organizing, and linking attributes within LCA studies to improve transparency and consistency in modeling. It includes four core components: (i) a conceptual framework for attribute extraction in LCA studies, (ii) a cause–effect mapping structure linking LCA elements, system components, and derived attributes, (iii) a structured clarification of LCA components and their associated elements, and (iv) a specification of LCA attributes along with their corresponding measurement definitions.

Together, these elements provide a coherent modeling foundation that supports traceability from system components to impact-relevant attributes, enabling improved interpretation of LCA results and facilitating further methodological development. This compendium is intended to ensure reproducibility, enable reuse in future research, and provide a citable reference for the conceptual and structural building blocks of the attribute-based LCA modeling approach.

Keywords: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), attribute-based modeling, system mapping, cause-effect modeling, sustainability assessment

Figure 1. A conceptual approach to map attribute extraction for LCA studies

Table 1. Clarification of components and their associated LCA elements

Element	Component	Definition
Approach	Goal & scope definition	Specifies the purpose, boundaries, and functional unit of the study.
	Inventory Analysis	Collects data on inputs and outputs within the system boundaries.
	Types of LCA	Different methodologies such as Cradle-to-Grave, Cradle-to-Gate, etc.
	Impact Assessment	Evaluates potential environmental impacts.
Method	Impact Assessment Model	Describes the mathematical models and algorithms used to evaluate impacts.
	Characterization Factors	Converts inventory data into potential impacts.
	Weighting	Prioritizes impacts based on significance.
	Midpoint vs Endpoint Approaches	Midpoints (intermediate results) vs. Endpoints (final results on areas of protection like human health, ecosystems).
	Normalization	Adjusts results to a common reference.
Database	Data Quality management	Accuracy, precision, and reliability of the data.
	Geographical Coverage	Specificity to certain regions or global data.
	Temporal Coverage	Relevance to the time period of interest.
	Technological Coverage	Reflects current or specific technologies.
	Completeness	Comprehensive inclusion of relevant processes and flows.
	Transparency	Availability of metadata and documentation.
Tool	User Interface	Ease of use, visualization capabilities, and user support.
	Functionality	Ability to perform goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation.
	Compatibility (with databases/methods)	Interoperability with various databases and methods.
	Flexibility (Tool)	Customization options and adaptability to different LCA approaches.
	Support & Updates	Availability of technical support and regular updates.

Table 2. Specification of LCA attributes and their respective measures

Component	Attribute	Definition	Measurement
Goal & scope definition	Granularity <i>Quantitative</i>	Detail level of data, such as the proportion of site-specific data versus generic data.	Percentage of primary data sources versus secondary (or aggregate) data sources.
Inventory Analysis	Data Requirement <i>Quantitative</i>	Volume of data points required or the size of the dataset.	Count total number of inventory flows required; check types of input/output data.
Goal & scope definition, Types of LCA	Scope (System Boundary) <i>Quantitative</i>	Coverage of life cycle stages (e.g., cradle-to-grave).	Number of life cycle stages included in the study.
Inventory Analysis	Data Sources <i>Quantitative</i>	Number and quality of data sources used.	Assess number and type of data sources
Inventory Analysis	Resolution <i>Quantitative</i>	Level of detail in data representation.	The scale at which data is recorded (e.g., per unit, per product category, or at an industry level)
Inventory Analysis	Integration <i>Qualitative</i>	Degree to which different datasets and methods are compatible.	Number of successfully integrated datasets or methods.
Goal & scope definition	Flexibility (Modeling) <i>Qualitative</i>	Adaptability of an approach to different scenarios.	Number of adaptations possible or time required to adapt the approach for new contexts.
Types of LCA, Impact Assessment	Complexity <i>Quantitative</i>	Level of sophistication in analysis.	Count modeling steps; assess computational requirements
Impact Assessment Model	Standards / Adherence <i>Qualitative</i>	Degree to which the method aligns with recognized standards (ISO 14040/44, ILCD) for modeling, documentation, and reporting.	Count of ISO standards met or rated compliance level (e.g., % adherence to ISO 14044).
Impact Assessment Model	Modeling Assumptions <i>Qualitative</i>	Simplifications, heuristics, or default choices used in the method that may affect accuracy or representativeness.	Identify and categorize assumptions (Minor / Moderate / Strong)
Characterization Factors	Spatial / Temporal Resolution <i>Quantitative</i>	Degree to which the method accounts for geographical and time-specific variations in impact modeling.	Count number of spatial regions or time steps modeled.
Impact Assessment Model	Customizability <i>(Qualitative)</i>	Degree of method adaptability.	Rate adaptability (Low / Medium / High)
Weighting	Aggregation Level <i>Qualitative</i>	Level of aggregation of results, e.g., midpoint (detailed) vs endpoint (aggregated damage categories).	Classify method as midpoint / endpoint / hybrid.
Midpoint vs Endpoint Approaches	Uncertainty Characteristics <i>Quantitative</i>	Degree to which the method quantifies and propagates uncertainties (parameter, model, scenario).	Monte Carlo simulation; calculate 95% confidence interval or standard deviation.
Normalization	Reference Appropriateness <i>Qualitative</i>	Suitability of normalization or reference values for the specific region, time frame, and study context.	Rate match to context (Good / Medium / Poor). e.g., Global normalization factors used for EU study = Medium
Weighting	Subjectivity <i>Qualitative</i>	Degree of value-based or normative influence in weighting impacts (e.g., stakeholder preferences, political priorities).	Classify weighting principle (Equal / Stakeholder / Policy-based) e.g., Stakeholder-weighted scores = High

Component	Attribute	Definition	Measurement
Data Quality management	Data Quality <i>Qualitative/ Quantitative</i>	Accuracy, precision, and reliability of inventory data, including completeness and representativeness for the study context.	Pedigree matrix scoring; compare reported vs. actual measurements; evaluate uncertainty.
Geographical Coverage	Geographical Coverage <i>Quantitative</i>	Extent of regional coverage.	Number of regions covered or region-specific data points included.
Temporal Coverage	Temporal Coverage <i>Quantitative</i>	Age of data.	Compare dataset year vs. study year.
Technological Coverage	Technological Coverage <i>Qualitative</i>	Extent to which the database represents current or specific technologies relevant to the study system.	Evaluate process match; categorize as Low / Medium / High. e.g., Modern steel production processes included = High
Completeness	Completeness (Database) <i>Qualitative/ Quantitative</i>	Degree to which all relevant processes, flows, and life cycle stages are included in the database.	Count processes and flows; check for missing stages or flows. e.g., 300 flows included per FU
Transparency	Transparency <i>Qualitative</i>	Availability of metadata and documentation.	Open/closed documentation scale; evaluate metadata completeness.
User Interface	Usability / User-friendliness <i>Qualitative</i>	Usability and ease of navigation.	System Usability Scale (SUS) score 0–100.
Functionality	Computational Capabilities <i>Qualitative</i>	Speed and resource usage during calculations.	Time to solve model (seconds); RAM usage.
Compatibility (with databases/methods)	Interoperability <i>Qualitative</i>	Ability to import/export different formats.	Supported formats count.
Impact Assessment model, Flexibility (Tool)	Customizability <i>Qualitative</i>	Degree to which user can modify tool settings.	Level (Low/Med/High).
Support & Updates	Support & Updates <i>Qualitative</i>	Availability of technical support, maintenance, and software updates to ensure reliability over time.	Rate frequency of updates, availability of help resources.

Figure 2. Cause-effect mapping between LCA elements, their components, and extracted attributes